

Management of Islamic Education Institutions in Human Resource Development in the Era of Disruption

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to reveal the management of Islamic educational institutions in developing human resources in the era of disruption with the research focus covering: 1) Analysis of the response of Islamic educational institutions in developing human resources in the era of disruption, 2) Analysis of the transformation of human resources in the era of disruption. Islamic educational institutions after participating in development activities in the era of disruption. 3) Identify challenges and opportunities for Islamic educational institutions in developing human resources in the era of disruption. This study used a qualitative approach with case study design. Data was collected by using interview, observation and documentation techniques. Data analysis techniques include data coding, data classification, data reduction, data exposure, research findings. Technique of data validity using source triangulation. Research informants are the principal, the person in charge of human resources, educators and education staff. The results of the study show that: 1) Analysis of the response of Islamic educational institutions in developing human resources in the era of disruption includes a) Planning for human resource development in the Era of disruption, b) Organizing human resource development in the Era of disruption, c) Directing resource development human resources in the era of disruption, d) Coordination of human resource development in the era of disruption, e) Supervision of human resource development in the era of disruption, 2) analysis of the transformation of human resources for human resources at Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu after participating in development activities in the era of disruption namely mindset, motivation, knowledge, abilities and skills. 3) Identification of challenges and opportunities in developing human resources in the era of disruption, namely a) rate of change, b) commitment of human resources, c) leadership, d) Infrastructure, e) Success and Competency Trap.

KEYWORDS: Management, Islamic Educational Institutions, Development, Human Resources, Era of Disruption.

INTRODUCTION

The current social order is facing a major shock, as illustrated by several experts, namely the Disruption Era. The era of disruption is formed as an accumulation of lifestyle changes and increasing global competition. One reason is the acceleration in the use of information technology. This phenomenon encourages everyone to think about how to apply future science in present conditions. The era of disruption is an era of change from manual to all digital. In the era of disruption, drastic changes occurred, changing the order of human life in various fields, including in the service sector.

The phenomenon of industrial disruption can be seen in the 1970s. At that time, the computer technology industry was controlled by IBM and not all offices could afford it. However, as development progressed, the position of IBM which seemed to have a monopoly on computer system software was shifted by Bill Gates through his masterpiece Microsoft. Almost like a cycle, even after its heyday, Microsoft began to shift with the findings of Google in the 1990s. Until now Google seems to rule the world in the era of modern technology in the 21st century. The monopoly position owned by Google generates great added value because with it they are able to carry out developments that other corporates cannot. In Indonesia, related to the phenomenon of the impact of disruption, we can see the current condition, conventional buying and selling outlets are no longer able to survive. Modern retail stores have been uprooted by the rise of online buying and selling. Another example, Blue Bird, which used to be a big giant in the transportation service business, is now participating in the new industry player, transportation company based on GoJek's online application. According to Ni Putu Suda Nurjani (2019), the industry trend is changing from the owning economy to the sharing economy, so industry players must be more careful in making changes to maintain business sustainability.

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According to Wayan Lasmawan (2019), the emergence of technological application innovations such as Uber or Gojek will inspire the birth of similar applications that are very influential in the world of education. For example MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) and AI (Artificial Intelligence). MOOC is an online learning innovation that is designed to be open to sharing and being connected or networked with one another. This principle marks the beginning of the democratization of knowledge which creates opportunities for us to make productive use of the world of technology. With online learning, it will accelerate the dissemination of knowledge. AI is an artificial intelligence engine designed to do a specific job in helping individualized learning. Because the Navy is able to search for the desired information while presenting it quickly, accurately and interactively. Both MOOC and AI are likely to become rule model based for the development of models and instruments of future educational practice.

To face the era of disruption requires skilled and high-quality human resources in various sectors, one of which is in the field of education. According to the results of Kuswanto's research cited by Yulizar and Farida (2019), the solution for disruption for teachers is self-development. Education will progress if human resources are able to innovate and renew. The efficiency resulting from the development of human resource performance is a competitive advantage for the organization (Meithiana Indrasari: 2017). According to Krismiyati (2017) human resource development can be defined as a set of systematic and planned activities designed to facilitate employees with the skills needed to meet job demands, both now and in the future. As well as a planned and sustainable effort made by the organization in improving employee competence and organizational performance through training, education, and development programs.

In the era of disruption, teachers need to have a new mindset, rich in innovation, flexible, creative and adaptive to changing times. In the era of disruption, educators must as soon as possible start changing their old approaches, models, and strategies and be flexible in adapting and elaborating new things more quickly. The presence of digital technology must be utilized in such a way by learners to make their learning more innovative, interesting, empowering for their students. Based on the results of Dwiningrum's research (2018) that teachers in the 21st century must change the mindset from a fix-mindset to a growth mindset. A teacher is able to design education with a multiliteracy pedagogical planning approach by preparing students to have various competencies. Along with this, the principles that must be put forward by students in this era of disruption are: (1) as soon as possible out of the comfort zone of the past, (2) working with clear targets or achievements, (3) conducting a series of meaningful teaching, (4) getting used to being an innovator and inspiration for the class and its students, and (5) building an expert autonomous mentality (Wayan Lasmawan: 2019).

Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu is an educational institution that responds to the demands of the era of disruption. Al Hikmah Boarding School High School has been established since 2017. However, complete information about this institution can be easily accessed on social media. Both through social media such as Instagram and Facebook as well as the official website of the Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu High School. In addition to basic school data, information regarding the development of students can also be accessed by parents virtually as a form of report. Even at Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu, a special application for monitoring student learning was created through the Information Technology-based Learning and Content Management System – LCMS. So that this application is able to show the best achievements of students, and what things still need to be improved from students at Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu. Thus, the use of digital technology in teaching and learning activities and education management is a basic ability that must be mastered by all elements of the institution's human resources.

In addition to responding to the development of information and communication technology, this Boarding School was built with the concept of Islamic teachings and skills for the 21st Century. Every child is taught to be a pious person, able to take responsibility, optimize potential and be able to bring change and improvement in the future. Therefore, aware of the need for humans who have an adaptive spirit and are able to learn new things in the future, education at Al Hikmah Boarding School High School tries to instill a learner spirit with a self-directed learning approach. With this approach, students are given the opportunity to arrange their own study schedule, are expected to be able to explore the root of the problem and find solutions, and determine how much material is needed for future achievements. The goal is to create a strong independent person to face the changes in the future.

Al Hikmah Boarding School High School understands the importance of human resources who spearhead the success of graduates. So educational institutions continue to develop. Because it is different from the previous human resource development. The development of human resources in the era of disruption emphasizes increasing the ability of educators and education personnel to be able to operationalize information technology. Especially the Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu High School which uses a self-directed learning system supported by the LCMS (Learning Content Management System) platform. Thus, it requires teachers to be able to operationalize it. Because LCMS is a platform that continues to be developed, teachers must also carry out self-development both from making modules, learning media and evaluating learning based on LCMS.

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METHOD

The approach used in this research is qualitative with the type of case study research at Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu High School. Sources of data obtained are grouped into two, namely primary and secondary data sources. Primary data sources come from interviews with informants, namely the principal, the person in charge of human resources, educators and education staff. Meanwhile, secondary data sources come from documents that support this research. The data collection techniques used are interview, observation and documentation methods. Data analysis techniques were carried out through the stages of data collection, data coding, classification, reduction, and data exposure. Test the validity of the data using triangulation of sources and methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. The Response of Islamic Educational Institutions in Developing Human Resources in the Era of Disruption

Human resource development is a series of activities carried out systematically, planned, and continuously in order to improve the competence of human resources by means of education and training. According to Muliawaty (2019), the era of disruption is an opportunity as well as a challenge to modern human resource management practices. The opportunity is in order to improve the performance of leaders and the readiness of employees as human resources towards the best performance, improve an organization, the organization becomes more efficient, effective and competitive. Including facing the challenges of the global era. According to Dacholfany (2017) management strategies and techniques are carried out by Islamic educational institutions in improving the quality of human resources by aligning programs and resources with the behavior of the academic community to achieve targeted performance.

The response of Islamic educational institutions in developing human resources in the era of disruption carried out by Al Hikmah Boarding Boarding Batu High School is:

1. Planning of Islamic Educational Institutions in the Development of Human Resources in the Era of Disruption

Planning for human resource development in the era of disruption carried out by schools involves all elements of existing human resources. Meanwhile, decision making is at the helm of the institution. This planning is done based on needs analysis. The analysis is carried out both in terms of quantity and quality. The hallmark of each teaching staff in this school is to have specifications as a religion teacher, Counseling Guidance teacher and Study field teacher. These three qualifications must be owned by every teacher when they want to become a teacher. Even though they come from various general college education backgrounds. Then, to face this era of disruption, there are six basic capacities that must be possessed by high school teachers at Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu, namely 1) Educational Capacity, 2) Technological Capacity, 3) Globalization Capacity, 4) Future Strategies capacity, 5) Counselor Capacity and 6) Spiritual Capacity.

Based on the results of Haris' research (2019) that in implementing changes to the education system in this industrial era, it is necessary to change the application of the system in Islamic educational institutions towards digital transformation. In addition to core competencies, educators are also required to have qualifications and supporting competencies which include: agility, innovation, creativity, anticipation, experimentation, open-mindedness, and networking. The competencies needed to be successful in the era of disruption and developed by educational institutions at all levels are the "Seven Survival Skills for the 21st Century" namely: (1) Critical thinking and problem solving, (2) Collaboration across networks, (3) Agility and adaptability, (4) Initiative and entrepreneurship, (5) Accessing and analyzing information, (6) Effective oral and written communication, 7) Curiosity and imagination (Tony Wager : 2008).

2. Organizing Islamic Educational Institutions in Developing Human Resources in the Era of Disruption

The organization of human resource development carried out by schools is based on the needs and interests of the educators and education personnel. This is done to obtain efficient and maximum results. To carry out this organization, the first step taken by the institution was to ask educators and education staff to conduct a Self-Evaluation and Continuing Professional Education. After that, the institution will do the grouping based on these needs.

3. Direction of Islamic Educational Institutions in the Development of Human Resources in the Era of Disruption

The leader is one of the vital organs for an Islamic educational institution. Leaders have a role to mobilize all existing resources within the institution. Both through instructions and motivation. The principal of Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu develops human resources with direction and motivation. The direction given is to be able to carry out self-development both organized by the foundation and institutions outside the foundation. Meanwhile, the direction given to develop, especially during the pandemic, is by participating in various webinars. So, it is not surprising that in a period of approximately three months they were able to participate in 400 types of webinars from various human resources. Based on the results of research conducted by

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Yulizar and Farida (2019) that the leadership of school principals in the era of disruption as managers includes 1) planning programs, 2) organizing programs, 3) moving programs, 4) monitoring and evaluating programs, and 5) as developers. culture.

4. Coordination of Islamic Educational Institutions in the Development of Human Resources in the Era of Disruption

Coordination is one of the management steps taken by Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu in developing human resources. This is done to optimize the results of the development. The form of coordination carried out is communicating the needs of the institution and the willingness and ability of human resources. This coordination can be done during the morning briefing or other meetings.

5. Control of Islamic Educational Institutions in Human Resource Development in the Era of Disruption

After the educators and education staff develop both by attending training, workshops and training. They are required to make reports and present the results or knowledge gained when participating in the training to their colleagues. Based on an example of a report on human resource development activities. The systematics for writing activity reports include 1) Title and Activity Organizers; 2) Implementation 3) Resource persons and activity participants 4) Activity Materials; 5) Knowledge gained; 6) Documentation; 7) Cover; 8) Attachments consist of certificates, materials and practicals. The control carried out during the pandemic is by utilizing information technology such as holding meetings via zoom and google meet.

B. Human Resources Transformation after Following Development in the Era of Disruption

Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu is one of the Islamic educational institutions that is concerned with the development of human resources. This attention is carried out because of the awareness that the main core of an Islamic educational institution is human resources. Therefore, a series of developments continues to be carried out to form educators and education personnel who have superior competencies. The following are some of the transformations of human resources at Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu after participating in development activities in the era of disruption, namely:

1. Mindset

Mindset is one part that needs to be developed in an educator and education staff. Mindset is a mindset that is owned by someone who becomes a frame in thinking and acting. According to Rhenald Kasali, mindset is the way humans think which is determined by the settings we make before thinking and acting (Rhenald Kasali: 2018). It is not surprising that constructing a mindset is the main concept in conducting coaching by a training institution or agency.

The changes that occurred by the human resources of Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu High School after participating in education and training activities in the era of disruption were the establishment of a disruptive mindset. There is a change in mindset to continue to make improvements and improvements to the competencies possessed. Human resource awareness of the changing times that continue to occur. Require educators and education staff to continue to develop and innovate. Changes in the times that occur without harmonizing changes in the competence of educators and educational staff will result in these human resources being left behind. Based on the results of research conducted by Lasmawan (2019) that the principles that must be put forward by students are 1) Get out of the comfort zone of the past, 2) Work with clear targets or achievements. 3) Conduct a series of meaningful teaching, 4) Get used to being an innovator and inspiration. 5) Build an expert autonomous mentality.

2. Motivation

Motivation is an impulse in moving one's soul and behavior to act. There are two ways that can be done to increase this motivation. First, by building awareness from within the person. Second, by looking for triggers that come from outside the individual itself. Human resource development activities, both education and training, are part of the institution's strategy in motivating educators and education staff to be more productive. This is what Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu has done. To continue to maintain the spirit of its human resources. By conducting daily coaching and participating in various trainings. With the hope that it will bring new, more productive passion for the progress of the institution.

According to Kertajaya, one of the professional development models with the pattern of "growth with character" is character-based professional development using an excellence model. Excellence (excellence) which has the meaning that the teacher must have certain advantages in the field and the world, in a way; 1) Commitment or purpose, namely having a commitment to always be in the corridor of goals in carrying out their activities in order to achieve excellence; 2) Opening your gift or ability, which is having the ability to find one's potential; 3) Being the first and the best you can be or motivation, which is having a strong motivation to be the first and the best in their field; and 4) Continuous improvement, which is always making continuous improvements (Ali Mudlofir: 2013).

3. Knowledge and Skills

Knowledge and skills are the main objectives of human resource development. Especially in the era of disruption, the development carried out by an educational institution is certainly different from development in general. In the era of disruption, the development of knowledge and skills of human resources is more towards the development of information technology skills.

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Although basically the transformation of human resource competencies must be in accordance with the objectives of carrying out the development. Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu has six basic capacities that educators must possess. The capacities that must be possessed by educators are 1) Educational Capacity, 2) Technological Capacity, 3) Globalization Capacity, 4) Future Strategies capacity, 5) Counselor Capacity and 6) Spiritual Capacity. Thus, the development carried out should be oriented towards increasing this capacity.

Based on the results of Dwiningrum's research (2018), it is very important to develop teacher resilience because it is related to the development of professional identity which is very much needed in the challenges of the 21st century. In addition, resilient teachers are able to turn disruption into opportunities, teachers are able to develop agility and not be trapped by rigidity that causes the learning process to become meaningless in the era of the internet of things. According to Kertajaya, one of the professional development models with the pattern of "growth with character" is character-based professional development using the Passion for Professionalism model. Passion For Professionalism is a strong will that intrinsically animates all patterns of professionalism, namely; 1) Passion for knowledge; namely the spirit to always increase knowledge either through formal or informal means; 2) Passion for business; namely the spirit to perform perfectly in carrying out its business, duties and mission; 3) Passion for service; namely the spirit to provide the best service for what is their responsibility; 4) Passion for people; namely the spirit to realize devotion to others on the basis of humanity (Ali Mudlofir: 2013).

C. Challenges and Solutions of Islamic Education Institutions in Developing in the Era of Disruption

Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu is one of the Islamic educational institutions that is concerned with developing human resources in the era of disruption. The challenges faced are varied. The following are the challenges faced and solutions made by Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu High School in developing human resources in the era of disruption, namely:

1. Rate Of Change

The rate of change is one of the challenges faced by an Islamic educational institution including the AL Hikmah Boarding School Batu in developing human resources in the era of disruption. This occurs as a result of the development of the era of disruption. Developments that occur in this era can not be predicted accurately. Even for forecasting the long-term human resource development planning of the institution, it is difficult. This challenge occurs because the development of human resources and the rate of change of the times are not directly proportional. The changing times that are not in line with the development of human resources have caused educational institutions to lag behind. Because, if times change, of course, consumer needs for education will also be different.

To face the challenge of the rate of change, the steps taken by the institution are to instill in educators and education a fast response mindset. Response to changing times and consumer education needs. Based on the results of research by Wayan Lasmawan (2019) that in the era of disruption, educators must immediately start changing their old approaches, models and strategies and be flexible in adapting and elaborating new things more quickly. Ecosystems require educators with a new mindset, rich in innovation or learning content, flexible, and adaptive to a rapidly changing world.

2. Human resources Commitment

The commitment of human resources is one part of the challenges faced by Islamic educational institutions in carrying out development. The lack of willingness and ability of educators and education staff in carrying out development will have an impact on the quality of human resources themselves. Which in turn will affect the quality of Islamic educational institutions. In carrying out development, of course, must be based on the willingness and ability of educators and education staff. This is done to get more optimal results.

The efforts made by the institution are to provide motivation and instill a good driver mentality. Driver mentality means that human resources have an adaptive mentality to the needs of the institution. According to Renald Kasali, an organization that is agile and dynamic in adapting to navigate the ocean of disruption is an organization that has human resources with a good driver mentality, not a passenger (Renald Kasali: 2018).

3. Leadership

Leaders are one of the key indicators in improving the quality of human resources of an educational institution. Leaders take a role in regulating and managing human resource development in the era of disruption. Therefore, we need leaders who are able to drive educational institutions in achieving their goals, vision and mission. To face these challenges, the principal of the Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu High School actively participates in self-development. Both academic development, managerial, leadership and supervision. Based on the results of Haris' research (2019) that leaders are required to be reliable drivers for an educational institution. Thus, managerial competence alone is not enough. But it must also be accompanied by the ability to lead.

In addition to self-development, the principal also coordinates with educators and education staff when determining the development to be followed by these human resources. This coordination is carried out so that the development of human

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resources is not only based on the will of the leadership. But also based on the desires and needs of these human resources. As stated by Dacholfany (2017) that effective leaders must carefully look at people's preferences. People who have low preferences and abilities with low empowerment will be complaining. On the other hand, people who have high preferences and abilities are maximally empowered, so they will be adaptive.

4. Infrastructure

Human resource development in the era of disruption is mostly done through teleconference media such as zoom and google meet, especially during the pandemic. Such a development method must of course be supported by adequate information technology. Like a computer or laptop and a stable network. However, the big challenge in developing this method is the stability of the network. Even though the network or signal has been set up properly, sometimes problems arise when development activities are carried out. The strategy taken to overcome such problems is the creativity of these human resources. Both provide a second network option or so. This method is done when problems occur on the first network.

5. Success and Competency Trap

The success trap is one of the challenges for an agency, including educational institutions. Where an educational institution is trapped with past successes, feeling satisfied with these successes and achievements. Thus, they are unwilling and unable to identify the agile steps taken by other agencies. While the competency trap is the institution that feels the most competent and cannot be competed. So it neglects to allocate the budget for the development of human resource competencies. Such challenges occur in institutions that already have popularity in the eyes of education consumers.

To face the challenges above, Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu High School continues to improve and evaluate LCMS. Even when Work from Home and Learn from Home happen. The institution combines LCMS and Zoom to support learning activities. According to Renald Kasali, maintaining the old one is not enough. Also have to create something new. So as to obtain better results (Renald Kasali: 2018).

CONCLUSION

After conducting research and analyzing research data, there are several conclusions that are in accordance with the research results, namely:

1. The response of Islamic education institutions at Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu in developing human resources in the era of disruption includes 1) Planning for human resource development in the era of disruption, there are six capacities that must be possessed by human resources in the era of disruption including Educational Capacity, Technological Capacity, Globalization Capacity, Future Strategies capacity, Counselor Capacity and Spiritual Capacity. 2) Organizing human resource development in the era of disruption, organizing based on the needs and preferences of human resources through Self-Evaluation and Continuing Professional Education. 3) Directing the development of human resources in the era of disruption, one form of institutional response is to direct and motivate human resources to carry out self-development in the era of disruption. 4) Coordination of human resource development in the era of disruption, the coordination carried out is by carrying out two-way communication between institutions and human resources related to the needs of human resource development. 5) Supervision of human resource development in the era of disruption, supervision carried out after participating in development activities both training and workshops is by making reports, presenting and making products (on certain trainings).
2. Transformation of human resources at Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu after participating in development activities in the era of disruption, including 1) Mindset. The development of a disruptive mindset, namely a change in mindset to continue to make improvements and improvements to the competencies possessed. 2) Motivation. Passion to be more productive. And 3) Knowledge, Abilities and Skills. The fundamental change that occurs is the ability to operationalize information technology. There are six capacities that must be developed in every human resource, including Educational Capacity, Technological Capacity, Globalization Capacity, Future Strategies capacity, Counselor Capacity and Spiritual Capacity.
3. Challenges and opportunities in developing human resources in the era of disruption include 1) rate of change, the rate of change is one of the challenges faced by the high school Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu in developing human resources in the era of disruption. The opportunity that institutions have in facing these challenges is to instill in human resources a fast response mindset. 2) Commitment of human resources, to face these challenges the opportunities that the institution has are with motivation and good mental drivers. 3) Leadership, to face this challenge the Principal of Al Hikmah Boarding School Batu participates in self-development, both academic, managerial, leadership and supervision development. 4) Infrastructure, a development challenge carried out through teleconference media such as zoom and google meet, namely network instability. The opportunity that the institution has is that it will have creative and strong human resources. 5) Success and Competency Trap, the opportunity for the institution is to continue to improve and evaluate LCMS.

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